

Modelling fluid-induced seismicity rates associated with fluid injections: examples related to fracture stimulations in geothermal areas

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SUMMARY

In this paper, we present a model for describing relationships between fluid-induced seismicity and operational parameters of fluid injections. Considering seismic sequences occurring during sustained fluid injections, we present a novel covariate approach in which a probability distribution is defined as a basic template function for modelling the interevent times (i.e. the time intervals between consecutive events), and the possible dependencies on operational parameters are modelled writing the parameters of the probabilistic model in terms of deterministic functions of explanatory covariates that are selected from the operational data. The implemented model is tested using data from two cases of reservoir stimulations in geothermal systems (The Geysers, US and Cooper Basin, Australia). We have found that a template exponential distribution of interevent times, with a linear function relating the logarithm of the distribution's μ parameter and the logarithm of the injection rate, is the model that better describes the observations in all the analysed cases. This result suggests that the μ parameter and the injection rate have a power-law relationship. The value of the power-law exponent, α_1 , is an indicator of the relative change in the seismicity rate associated with a relative change in the injection rate, and it results particularly important for understanding the behaviour of seismicity at high injection rates. $\alpha_1 = -1$ indicates the special case of a linear relationship between seismicity rate and injection rate (which usually is the model assumed in the literature); conversely, $\alpha_1 > -1$ ($\alpha_1 < -1$) indicates that the relative change in the seismicity rate associated with a relative change in the injection rate is lower (higher) than the relative change expected by assuming a linear relationship between these two parameters. Regarding the cases analysed in this paper, the exponent of the power law varies between -1.04 and -0.78 in The Geysers, and between -1.22 and -0.73 in Cooper Basin. While no clear temporal trends are observable in the α_1 values obtained for The Geysers, in Cooper Basin α_1 increased as the stimulation tests proceeded (from an initial value of $\alpha_1 = -1.22$ calculated for the first fracture initiation test to $\alpha_1 = -0.73$ associated with the third fracture initiation test). This behaviour can be a consequence of the so-called Kaiser effect indicating that, to trigger events, the pore pressure during new injections must exceed the values already reached in previous injection operations. Finally, we also studied the gradual decline of seismicity rates in the post-injection phases in Cooper Basin using the modified Omori law. We explored this data set for looking, in particular, if there exists a pattern between the parameters controlling the post-injection seismicity decay rate and the characteristics of the precedent fluid injection.

Key words: Induced seismicity; Statistical Seismology; Probabilistic forecasting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Anthropic activities such as mining, underground fluid injection/extraction, or reservoir impoundments, have the potential of producing underground stress perturbations (e.g., Davies et al. 2013). Stress perturbations, in turn, are able to enhance (or to inhibit) the occurrence of seismic events. Consequently, seismicity can be induced in zones where the anthropogenic stress perturbations meet favorable local geomechanical conditions.

The topic of induced seismicity has attracted greater attention in recent years, particularly because of several cases in which seismic sequences have been related to processes involving the high-pressure injection of fluids into the Earth's crust, as for example for waste-water disposal (e.g., Ellsworth 2013), operations in Enhanced Geothermal Systems (EGS, e.g., Majer et al. 2007) and hydraulic fracturing for recovery of hydrocarbons from unconventional sources (e.g., Davies et al. 2013).

According to the characteristics of the fluid pressure perturbation with respect to the stress field in the rock, the generated fluid-induced seismicity can be associated with different physical processes (e.g., Shapiro et al. 2007): on the one hand, if the pore pressure resulting from a fluid injection in low permeable rocks is larger than the minimum principal stress, a fracture can be created and the properties of the induced seismicity are mainly controlled by the process of hydraulic fracture growth (Rutledge et al. 2004; Shapiro et al. 2006). On the other hand, if the pore pressure resulting from a fluid injection is smaller than the minimum principal stress, then in a first approximation the development of induced seismicity is governed by the pressure diffusion in fluid saturated rocks (Shapiro et al. 2007).

Fluid-induced seismic sequences can be observed during and after fluid injection operations. The seismicity rates observed during the injection phases exhibit a different temporal behaviour with respect to the decaying rate with time usually observed after the end of injections. The seismicity during the injection phases (the main target of the analyses in this paper) is usually clustered in time and space and may show a non-stationary behaviour; the non-stationarity is thought to be a direct consequence of the variability of the forcing processes resulting from fluid injections (e.g., Ake et al. 2005; Bachmann et al. 2011; Brodsky & Lajoie 2013).

Nevertheless, it is also possible that induced events produce themselves local stress changes which, in turn, may influence the evolution of the seismic sequence. Therefore, the complexity of the spatial and temporal distribution of fluid-induced seismic sequences is probably linked to the combined contribution of different source processes related to both fluid injections and seismic interactions.

As for naturally occurring seismic sequences, stochastic modelling has become an important tool to provide macroscopic descriptions of the temporal behaviour of fluid-induced seismicity. However, the literature in this field provides contrasting evidences for distinguishing the contribution of both fluid injections and seismic interactions in the resulting seismicity rates. For example, analyzing six catalogs from geothermal injection sites (from Soultz-sous-Forets and Basel), Langenbruch et al. (2011) suggested that the seismicity rate changes in the analysed cases are primarily related to changes of the injection flow rate and not

to the occurrence of aftershocks; they argue that occurring events seem not to be causally related to each other or, if it exists, this relation is very weak. In contrast, Bachmann et al. (2011) analysed the Basel data set to test the forecasting performance of two classes of statistical models: the Reasenbergs and Jones model (RJ, Reasenbergs & Jones 1989, 1990, 1994), and the Epidemic-type aftershock models (ETAS, Ogata 1988; Hainzl & Ogata 2005), which differentiates a background rate and a term of (aftershock-like) triggered events. In particular, Bachmann et al. (2011) considered a *modified* ETAS model in which the background rate term of ETAS is dependent on the flow rate, concluding that the modified ETAS model is much more able to adjust non-stationary seismicity in the studied case. It is therefore implicitly assumed that earthquake interactions play a role in the development of that fluid-induced seismic sequence. Later, Mena et al. (2013) extended the Bachmann et al. (2011) work by including in the comparative analysis a third class of model, the Shapiro's model, in which the number of fluid-injection-induced earthquakes exceeding a given magnitude value increases approximately in proportion to the injected fluid volume, and where event interactions are neglected (Shapiro et al. 2007, 2010). Regarding the forecasting performance of the specific models, Mena et al. (2013) suggested that in the analysed case Shapiro's model performs better than the ETAS and RJ.

It seems reasonable that incorporating knowledge about the anthropogenic operational factors is a critical need for better understanding the processes underlying the generation of fluid-induced seismic sequences and for assessing the related seismic hazard (Walters et al. 2015). As briefly shown in the previous paragraphs, a number of attempts have been performed to model relationships or correlations between induced seismicity rates and operational parameters as the injection rate or the total injected volume (to nominate some, see e.g., Shapiro et al. 2007, 2010; Bachmann et al. 2011; Mena et al. 2013; Leptokarpoulos et al. 2018).

Examining in particular approaches in which the operational data are explicitly considered in the parameterization of stochastic models and used to forecast seismicity rates, most authors usually assume a linear relationship between the number of induced events and the correlated operational parameter considered [see e.g., the linear relationship between the number of induced events during an injection and the cumulated injected volume assumed by Shapiro et al. (2007, 2010), or the linear relationship between the background seismicity rate and the injection rate assumed in the modified ETAS model by Bachmann et al. (2011) and Mena et al. (2013)].

How accurate is such assumption? To answer this question, in this paper we develop and implement a simple stochastic modelling approach to explore possible relationships between fluid-induced seismicity rates and operational parameters characterizing fluid injections. Once a model has been identified and calibrated, it is then used to forecast seismicity rates by employing the selected injection-related parameter(s) as input data. The performance of the model is then assessed by comparing the seismicity rate forecasts with the actual seismicity recorded during fluid injections.

The analyses were performed using data from two geothermal areas: The Geysers (California, US) and Cooper Basin (Australia). These data sets are presented in Section 2.

It is worth noting that the Cooper Basin data set exhibits interesting periods in which no injections are performed and where the seismicity rates show a typical gradual decline with time. Consequently, using this data set we also studied the seismicity decay rate during non-injection phases, looking in particular if there exists a pattern between the parameters controlling the post-injection seismicity decay rate and the characteristics of the precedent fluid injection.

2 DATA

In this study we analyze fluid-induced seismicity from two different cases: The Geysers geothermal field (California, US, Fig. 1a), and the Cooper Basin geothermal field (Australia, Fig. 2a).

2.1 The Geysers data set

The Geysers is a producing geothermal field located about 100 km north of San Francisco, California (Fig. 1a). The reservoir is recharged by water injections to enhance the steam production and to prevent decline in reservoir pressure (e.g., Goyal & Conant 2010; Sanyal et al. 2010). Micro-seismicity has been used as a general tool for both monitoring fluid paths as well as to understand the response of the system to fluid injections (e.g., Majer & Peterson 2007).

In this study we use a cluster of seismicity located in the NW part of The Geysers geothermal field (Fig. 1a). The cluster consists of 1254 events occurred in the vicinity of Prati-9 and Prati-29 injection wells between 10 December 2007 and 20 August 2014 (Fig. 1b). The data set has been introduced by Martínez-Garzón et al. (2014), Kwiatek et al. (2015), and Martínez-Garzón et al. (2016), and is available as a data episode via the IS-EPOS platform of the EPOS (European Plate Observing) project.

The seismic catalog is composed by event locations (with an accuracy of about 50 m), moment magnitudes (calculated from original duration magnitudes), and a magnitude of completeness $M_c = 1.4$ (Martínez-Garzón et al. 2014; Kwiatek et al. 2015; Martínez-Garzón et al. 2016).

Injections in the Prati-9 well were carried on continuously in the recording period of the studied data set. Conversely, injections in the Prati-29 well were carried on from April 2010 to June 2013 (Fig. 1b). In total, 1.04×10^7 m³ of fluids were injected in both wells in the time window of 6.7 years considered in this study (7.15×10^6 m³ in Prati-9 and 3.29×10^6 m³ in Prati-29).

2.2 The Cooper Basin data set

The Cooper Basin case study is a deep Hot Dry Rock (HDR) project operated by the Geodynamics Limited company that began in early 2003 in the Cooper Basin geothermal field, Australia (Fig. 2a). The first well (Habanero-1) was drilled in early 2003 reaching a depth of 4421 m into the granitic basement (Soma et al. 2004). Habanero-1 was hydraulically stimulated between November and December 2003, injecting in total about 125731 bbl (~ 19990 m³) of water. First, several fracture initiation tests (FIT) were performed, including a test to evaluate the hydraulic characteristics of the fracture (long-term flow rate test injection, LTI). FITs and the

LTI preceded the main hydraulic stimulation of Habanero-1 (Extended injection or EXI) that started on 30 November 2003 (Asanuma et al. 2005b).

In each FIT test, a volume of water comprised between 100 and 200 m³ was injected in a time ranging between 2 and 13 hours; during the LTI test, about 950 m³ of water were injected in about 9.3 days; finally, the main hydraulic stimulation in the analysed data set (EXI) was performed injecting about 14600 m³ of water in about 9.3 days (Fig. 2b).

The data set used in this paper results from monitoring and data processing activities performed by Geodynamics Limited (Australia), the Central Research Institute of Electric Power Industry (CRIEPI, Japan), as well as reprocessing introduced by different authors (e.g., Soma et al. 2004; Asanuma et al. 2005a,b; Baisch et al. 2006). The available seismic catalog consists of 28323 seismic events recorded between 06 November 2003 and 07 April 2005. The magnitude of completeness considered in this study for this catalog is $M_c = -0.8$ (15431 events above M_c were identified).

The data was recorded by a monitoring network composed by 4 near-surface (~ 100 m depth) and 4 downhole (one at 1794 m and three at 200-400 m depth) seismic stations (Fig. 2a). More details regarding the monitoring can be found in Soma et al. (2004) and Asanuma et al. (2005b). The available technological data is composed by time series containing data of tubing pressure, manifold pressure, annulus pressure, slurry rate, clean rate, downhole rate and the total (cumulated) job volume. Fig. 2b shows the cumulated injected volume (top), and the temporal distribution of event occurrences plotted against events' magnitudes (bottom).

3 METHODOLOGY

Fluid-induced seismic activity can be observed during the fluid injection phases and in the post-injection phases (hereinafter called *free-response* phases, FRPs, to stress the fact that no fluid injections are performed in these periods).

To contextualize the analyses presented in this paper, let's consider the schematic representation of generic fluid injections presented in Fig. 3. For simplicity, we neglect any contribution from background natural seismicity. According to Fig. 3a, no fluid injection takes place before the time t_0 , and consequently no fluid-induced seismicity is recorded. At time t_0 fluids start to be injected at a constant rate (Fig. 3b) and, after a given *lag time* τ (i.e., the time delay between the injection start and the seismic response of the system), fluid-induced seismicity starts to occur (Fig. 3c). The first injection finishes at time t_1 . During the time interval $[t_1, t_2]$ no fluid injection occurs; nevertheless, in that time interval it is possible to record seismicity (see for example the seismicity recorded after the FIT-n and LTI tests in Cooper Basin, as shown in Fig. 2b). According to the scheme presented in Fig. 3, a new stimulation takes place between time t_2 and t_4 ; in this case, there is a change in the injection rate at time t_3 and, as in the previous case, seismic activity can be observed during the injection and for a while after end of the stimulation.

While there is evidence that seismicity rates during injection phases may be somehow correlated to the fluid injections, it is less clear which geomechanical and/or injection

Figure 1. (a) Location of seismic events in The Geysers geothermal field, with a zoom to the seismicity cluster close to the two injection wells Prati-9 and Prati-29 analysed in this paper. The well trajectories are represented as blue lines; the black triangles represent seismic stations. (b) Plot of the cumulated injected volume (in m^3 , top) in both Prati-9 and Prati-29 wells, and the time series of seismicity plotted against the event's magnitude (bottom).

parameters control the characteristic decay rate of seismicity after the end of injections (Majer et al. 2007; Langenbruch & Shapiro 2010). The main methodological development in this paper is focused on modelling induced seismicity during fluid injection phases (section 3.1). Nonetheless, the Cooper

Basin data set exhibits interesting time intervals in which no injections are performed and where the seismicity rates show a typical gradual decline as time passes. Therefore, we extend our analyses in the Cooper Basin case study to briefly

Figure 2. (a) Location of the seismic events induced during the stimulations in Cooper Basin (Habanero-1 injection well, blue point); the black triangles represent the seismic stations, and red circles identify events with $M > 1.0$. (b) Plot of the cumulated injected volume (in m^3 , top) and the time series of seismicity plotted against the event's magnitude (bottom).

discuss the behaviour of seismicity in post-injection phases (section 3.2).

3.1 Modelling seismicity rates during injection phases

The analysis of interevent times (IET; i.e. the time intervals between consecutive events) has contributed to the development of stochastic models able to provide macroscopic descriptions of the temporal behaviour of both natural and fluid-induced seismicity (e.g., Bak et al. 2002; Matthews et al. 2002; Corral 2006).

The analysis of IET is the base of the methodology presented in this paper for modelling seismicity rates during injection phases. We assume that all the event occurrences in the seismic catalog are associated with the fluid injection process (it implies that we neglect both event interactions and eventual background natural seismicity). Furthermore, we assume that there exists a probability distribution that characterizes the IET, and that it is possible to identify a relationship between the parameters characterizing fluid injections and the parameters of the IET distribution.

Assuming a homogeneous Poisson process (HPP) as the process characterizing the occurrence of seismic events in

Figure 3. Conceptual representation of a multi-stage stimulation in which multiple injections are separated by no-injection intervals defined here as *free-response phases*. Top: cumulated injected volume showing two injection episodes. Middle: The respective injection rate. Bottom: Representation of a typical temporal evolution of the seismicity induced by this kind of stimulations.

the time domain implies that the IET are distributed following an exponential distribution. This is the simplest case of a Poisson process of event occurrences and it has been suggested as a valid model in situations in which the flow rate of the fluid injection is approximately constant (e.g., Langenbruch et al. 2011). If we consider a HPP with constant intensity λ (where $\lambda = 1/\mu$ is the expected number of events per unit time, and μ the mean IET), the corresponding probability density function of IET (denoted as t^*) can be defined as:

$$f(t^*|\mu) = \frac{1}{\mu} e^{-\frac{t^*}{\mu}} \quad (1)$$

In this paper we explore the implementation of probabilistic models in which parameters characterizing fluid injection operations are actively taken into account in the modelling process. With this aim, we take under consideration the hypothesis that under constant forcing processes, the seismicity rates can be described considering a HPP. However, since the forcing process may be non-stationary, we implement a modelling procedure based on a covariate approach in which the parameters of the probability distribution are allowed to change as a function of one or more covariates of interest. Similar procedures are used, for example, in extreme value problems for the analysis of climato-

logical extremes considering climate change scenarios (see e.g., Coles 2001; Garcia-Aristizabal et al. 2015).

In practice, our approach consists in defining a probability distribution as a basic template; possible dependences of the analysed variable (IET in this case) on technological data are modelled writing the parameter(s) of the probability distribution in terms of deterministic functions of explanatory covariates that are selected from the operational data. Considering the exponential distribution presented in Eq. 1, the covariate model for this distribution can be written as:

$$f(t^*|\mu(\theta_k)) = \frac{1}{\mu(\theta_k)} e^{-\frac{t^*}{\mu(\theta_k)}} \quad (2)$$

where $\theta_k = (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k)'$ is a vector of k covariates considered.

Given a sample of m independent IET observations $t^* = (t_1^*, t_2^*, \dots, t_m^*)$ and the associated matrix of m values for k covariates $\theta = (\theta_{k,1}, \theta_{k,2}, \dots, \theta_{k,m})$ selected for the analysis, we define the log-likelihood function for the covariate exponential model as:

$$l[\mu(\theta); t_1^*, \dots, t_m^*] = \sum_{j=1}^m \ln \left(\frac{1}{\mu(\theta_{k,j})} \right) - \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{t_j^*}{\mu(\theta_{k,j})} \quad (3)$$

where $\mu(\theta)$ is replaced by a deterministic expression linking the μ parameter to the set of k covariates of interest.

Figure 4. Plot of the IET data against the average injection rate during the related time interval for the (a) Cooper Basin and (b) The Geysers data set.

Under this hypothesis it is necessary to identify a valid proxy for representing the forcing process enhancing the generation of seismicity. Different authors have suggested the possible relation between fluid-injection rates and the respective fluid-induced seismicity rates (e.g., Shapiro & Dinske 2009; Langenbruch et al. 2011; Bachmann et al. 2011; Mena et al. 2013; Martínez-Garzón et al. 2014; Weingarten et al. 2015; Leptokarpoulos et al. 2018). Fig. 4 shows the plot of IETs against the average injection rate (at the respective time of event occurrence) calculated for both the Cooper Basin (Fig. 4a) and The Geysers (Fig. 4b) data sets. After a close inspection of these plots, it results plausible to consider the injection rate (i_r) as a possible covariate for modelling the distribution of IET of fluid-induced seismicity. In fact, the higher injection rates seem to be correlated with lower average IET. Therefore, we consider i_r as an informative parameter closely related to the forcing processes controlling seismicity rates.

Setting $\theta = (i_r)$ as the vector of ($k = 1$) covariates of interest in Eq. 2, the μ parameter of the exponential distribution can be written using deterministic functions of the injection rate. Considering the trends observed in Fig. 4, we test polynomial functions relating $\log(\mu)$ and $\log(i_r)$ as follows:

$$\log[\mu(i_r)] = \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_j (\log[i_r])^j \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha_j = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$ is a vector of coefficients of

the polynomial function relating the model parameter of the distribution with the identified covariate. A detailed description of the characteristics of the functions represented using Eq. 4 is presented in the Appendix A.

In order to compare the performance of the models tested using Eq. 4 with the linear relationship between the seismicity rates and the injection rate that is usually assumed, we also take explicitly in consideration the specific model:

$$\lambda(i_r) \equiv \frac{1}{\mu(i_r)} = a_0 + a_1 \cdot i_r \quad (5)$$

It is worth noting that the model in Eq. 5 can be considered a specific case of the general family of functions defined in Eq. 4 (which arises when $n = 1$, $a_0 = 0$, and $\alpha_1 = -1$).

The inference problem in this case is (i) to obtain the values of the α_j coefficients of the Eq. 4 (for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$); and (ii) to obtain the values of a_i of the Eq. 5. Afterwards, it is necessary to select the model that provides the best description of the data.

The input data (observations) are vectors containing the IETs and the correlated average injection rate (taking into account the eventual lag time τ). The inference of model parameter values is performed using a Bayesian approach based on a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method, following a similar approach as the one described in Garcia-Aristizabal et al. (2015) and Garcia-Aristizabal et al. (2016).

Since no genuine information is available to formulate a prior distribution in the domain of the model parameters, a

Table 1. Categories used as reference for the interpretation of the Bayes factors B_{kl} for the model selection, as presented in Raftery (1996) and modified from Jeffreys (1961)

$2\log_{10}(B_{kl})$	B_{kl}	Evidence for M_k
< 0	< 1	negative (supports M_l)
0 to 2	1 to 3	barely worth mentioning
2 to 5	3 to 12	positive
5 to 10	12 to 150	Strong
> 10	> 150	very strong

Normal distribution with high-variance is adopted for setting the prior information. Regarding the data distribution, the likelihood function is set considering the exponential model with covariates, $f(t^*|\mu(\theta))$, defined in Eq. 2.

Markov chains are constructed using the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm (Metropolis & Ulam 1949; Metropolis et al. 1953). After running the Markov chain, we remove the burn-in period and check the convergence of the simulated sequences (Geweke 1992). Summary statistics of the Markov chains are used to characterize the model parameter values; we use the median as the best estimation of each parameter, and two percentiles (16th and 84th) to define an uncertainty range.

Testing the performance of competing models requires also an adequate strategy to select the most appropriated model. The Bayes factor is a possible solution to the hypothesis testing and model selection in Bayesian inference problems (e.g., Kass & Raftery 1995; Raftery 1996; Lewis & Raftery 1997). The Bayes factor, B_{kl} , for comparing model M_k to Model M_l for observed data \mathbf{x} , is the ratio of the posterior odds for M_k against M_l to the prior odds. When the models M_k and M_l are equally probable a priori, then B_{kl} reduces to the ratio of the integrated (or marginal) likelihoods of the two models being compared (Lewis & Raftery 1997):

$$B_{kl} = \frac{f(\mathbf{x}|M_k)}{f(\mathbf{x}|M_l)} \quad (6)$$

The marginal likelihoods for the Bayes factor are calculated using the Laplace-Metropolis estimator (Raftery 1996; Lewis & Raftery 1997), which uses the MCMC posterior simulation output to estimate the integrated likelihoods. A detailed description of the method can be found in Raftery (1996), Lewis & Raftery (1997), and Garcia-Aristizabal et al. (2015). A summary of the Laplace-Metropolis estimator method used to estimate the marginal likelihoods is presented in the Appendix B.

The Bayes factor can be interpreted as a summary of the evidence provided by the data in favor of one specific model as opposed to another. Jeffreys (1961) suggested interpreting B_{kl} in half units on the \log_{10} scale and proposed different categories to assess the evidence against the reference model M_l (later modified by Raftery 1996, as twice the logarithm of the Bayes factor, which is on the same scale as the familiar deviance and likelihood-ratio test statistics). Table 1 summarizes the categories adopted in this work for the model selection and interpretation of results.

The model selection procedure is set to determine if a model in which the μ parameter is modulated by i_r (here-

inafter called non-stationary models, NSM, resulting from setting $n > 0$ in Eq. 4 as well as the linear relationship in Eq. 5) explains better the observations respect to assuming a stationary model (i.e., a case in which $\mu = \text{constant}$, resulting from setting $n = 0$ in Eq. 4). The model selection is performed by calculating the Bayes factors B_{n0} and B_{L0} (Eq. 6) that result from comparing the NSM M_n and M_L against the reference, stationary model (M_0). M_n are the polynomial functions resulting from setting $n > 0$ in Eq. 4, and M_L is the linear model defined in Eq. 5. The higher the B_{k0} , the more evidence provides the data in favor of the k -th model (see Table 1 for reference).

We implement the modelling approach presented in this section to analyze induced seismicity during the injection phases in the two data sets considered in this study. We also assess the capacity of the model to capture the possible relationship between fluid-induced seismicity and injection rates. To perform this assessment, each analysis is done by drawing two subsets of data from the original data set: a *training part* and a *forecasting part*. These two subsets of data come from two different, non-overlapping time windows.

The *training part* of the data set is used to determine, calibrate, and test candidate models relating the parameter(s) of the probability distribution (μ in this case) and the selected covariates (injection rate in this case), according to Eqs. 2, 4, and 5. The model selection is performed by calculating the Bayes factors B_{n0} and B_{L0} that, as previously stated, result from comparing the NSM M_n and M_L against the reference stationary model (M_0). The model with the highest Bayes factor is selected as the *preferred model*.

The *forecasting part* of the data is then used to assess the capacity of the *preferred* model to forecast seismicity rates induced by fluid injections. This assessment is performed by comparing the fluid-induced seismicity rates observed in the forecasting part of the data with the seismicity rate forecasts produced by the preferred model. It is worth noting that these seismicity forecasts are performed with a model that was calibrated with the training data set and that uses, as input data, the (known) values of the covariates (the injection rate in this case) from the forecasting part of the catalog.

In summary, the data analysis for modelling seismicity associated with fluid injection stimulations is performed according to the following general procedure:

(i) Evaluation of the eventual lag time τ between the start of the injection operations and the start of the seismic response of the system (i.e. the τ at which the correlation between seismicity rate and injection rate is maximum).

(ii) Inference of the parameter values of competing deterministic models relating the μ parameter of the exponential distribution and i_r . In this work, four deterministic models are tested (by setting $n = 0, 1, \text{ and } 2$ in Eq. 4 and the linear model in Eq. 5). The first three deterministic models are explicitly presented in Eq. A.2 in the Appendix A. This step is performed using a subset of the available data (i.e., the training part of the data set).

(iii) Assessment of the performance of the non-stationary models (i.e., those with $n > 0$ in Eq. 4 as well as the linear relationship presented in Eq. 5) respect to the stationary hypothesis ($n = 0$). This evaluation is performed using the

Bayes factor B_{kl} ; the model with the highest B_{kl} is selected as the *preferred model*.

(iv) Test the performance of the preferred model by comparing its ability to forecast the seismicity rates associated with (known) fluid injections. Such analysis is performed using data from injection phases different to the one(s) used for setting the model (i.e., the forecasting part of the data set). This assessment is performed by comparing the seismicity rate forecasts with the seismicity rates effectively observed.

3.2 Modelling post-injection seismicity rates (in Cooper Basin)

Contrary to the usual behaviour of induced seismicity during the injection phases, the sequences in the post-injection periods exhibit a gradual decline of seismicity rates as time passes. The signal of such a decay rate is well identifiable in the free-response phases in the Cooper Basin data.

Usually, the primary objective of modelling seismicity rates in post-injection phases is to identify the parameters controlling the seismicity decay rate to assess the expected time required for the seismicity to reach the background level after the termination of fluid injections (e.g., Bachmann et al. 2011; Langenbruch & Zoback 2016). Beyond this basic objective, in this work we are mainly interested in exploring if there exists a pattern between the parameters controlling the seismicity decay rate and the characteristics of the precedent fluid injection.

The statistical features of seismic sequences during FRPs can be modelled using decay functions, $\lambda(t)$, in an analogous way as done for the decay of aftershock seismicity after a triggering mainshock. Different functions have been proposed in the statistical-seismology literature for describing the nature of $\lambda(t)$, as for example the well-known modified Omori law (MOL, Omori 1894; Utsu 1961), exponential and inverse power-law decay functions (Vere-Jones & Davies 1966), or the Epidemic-type aftershock sequence model (ETAS, Ogata 1988, 1999).

Considering fluid-induced seismic activity, different authors have modelled the decay rate of seismicity after the end of injections using mainly the MOL (e.g., Langenbruch & Shapiro 2010; Bachmann et al. 2011; Langenbruch & Zoback 2016) and the ETAS (e.g., Bachmann et al. 2011; Mena et al. 2013) models. Langenbruch & Shapiro (2010), in particular, derived an analytical solution similar to the Omori law for describing the seismicity rate following the end of a fluid injection. While ETAS may intrinsically consider both the injection (through the modified background rate introduced by Bachmann et al. 2011) and the free-response phases, the MOL model is specifically used to model the seismicity recorded after the termination of fluid injections.

In this work we use the MOL model to analyze the decay rate of post-injection seismicity in Cooper Basin. It is worth noting that in fact we do not test the performance of the MOL model nor compare its behaviour respect to alternative models. Rather, we use this model to characterize the decay rate function and to explore possible relations with the parameters of the injection immediately preceding each FRP.

According to the MOL (Omori 1894; Utsu 1961), the decay rate of seismicity after a given triggering event can be described as

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{k}{(c+t)^p} \quad (7)$$

where $\lambda(t)$ is the number of events in the unit time; k is usually known as the productivity of aftershocks; t is the elapsed time since the triggering event (in this case the preceding fluid injection); p is the power-law exponent; and c is a parameter partially reflecting the effect of incomplete detection of small events shortly after the triggering event (Utsu et al. 1995). According to some authors c can be also considered as the time delay at which the decay rate initiates (e.g. Holschneider et al. 2012).

The MOL parameter values are determined using a two-step approach: in the first step, an initial solution is obtained using a classical Maximum Likelihood approach (MaxL, Ogata 1983). The second step is based on a Bayesian approach for model parameter inference; in this step, the MaxL solution is used to initialize a MCMC sampler in the parameter space. The Bayesian inference of the MOL model parameters is performed using the parameterization proposed by Holschneider et al. (2012), which is presented in the Appendix C.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Seismicity during fluid injections in The Geysers case study

The data set consists of a cluster of induced seismicity associated with the sustained injection of fluids covering about 6.7 years of technological and seismological data recorded in the northwest part of The Geysers geothermal field (Fig. 1). All the analyses are performed cumulating the fluid injections from Prati-9 and the nearby Prati-29 wells. According to Leptokarpoulos et al. (2018), the maximum correlation between injection and seismicity for this dataset occurs with a lag time $\tau \sim 2$ weeks.

Let us consider t_0 as the starting time of the data set (i.e., 10/12/2007). Two parallel strategies were adopted for selecting the *training* data: In the first approach (hereinafter called the *moving window* approach), a moving time window of a fixed length $\delta t = t_c - t_a$ is used to select the data for the model parameter estimation (i.e., the training part). t_a is the initial time of the time window, and t_c (or *current time* from the perspective of the forecasting exercise) represents the time of the last data point used for model parameter estimation; therefore, all the $t > t_c$ is the *forecasting* time window, and it defines the part of the catalog used for assessing the model's forecasting performance using as input information the i_r data only.

As time passes, the time window is slid forward in time and the model parameters of the competing models are recalculated. Past data recorded at time $t_0 < t < t_a$ are not considered anymore in the analysis. The updated preferred model is then used to forecast seismicity rates for times $t > t_c$ using the injection rate i_r from the (new) forecasting window.

In the alternative approach (hereinafter called the *cumulated* approach), all the data between t_0 and the current time t_c are considered *training part* and are used to redefine the model and to update the model parameter values. The

Figure 5. Model parameter estimation and seismicity rate forecasts in The Geysers case study using the *moving window approach*. The first column shows the data and the competing deterministic models fitted. The second column shows the cumulated number of events as a function of time (observed and forecasts performed using the preferred, power-law model): the observed seismicity is plotted using a red, solid line. Realizations of seismicity forecasts are shown using thin, gray lines; the seismicity forecast is summarized by the median of the solutions (solid black line), whereas uncertainty bounds are defined showing the 16th and 84th percentiles (dashed black lines). The examples shown in this figure correspond to model fitting and seismicity forecasts using the data from 18-months time windows starting on (a, b) 10-Dec-2007 [M1]; (c, d) 20-May-2009 [M4]; and (e, f) 20-May-2011 [M8].

updated model is then used to forecast seismicity rates for times $t > t_c$ (i.e., the *forecasting part*).

Considering the moving window approach, a time window of length $\delta t = 18$ months was chosen for selecting the *training data*; this choice is done since it ensures to have at least 100 seismic events at each time window used for

model parameter estimation. The model parameters were updated moving the δt window forward in time in steps of six months, obtaining in this way 8 sets of updated model parameters (hereinafter referred to as M1, . . . , M8).

Table 2 summarizes the Bayes factors calculated for comparing the performance of the NSM respect to the sta-

Table 2. Bayes factors B_{kl} calculated for model selection in The Geysers case study for models fitted using the moving window approach (M1 to M8). For each M, the highest Bayes factor is presented in bold.

Data used for model learning	$n = 0$	2Log(B_{n0}) [Degree of the polynomial function, Eq.4]		2Log(B_{L0}) [linear model as in Eq. 5]
		$n = 1$	$n = 2$	
M1	(Reference model)	22.8	18.4	18.2
M2	(Reference model)	30.2	25.0	25.2
M3	(Reference model)	32.2	29.0	26.9
M4	(Reference model)	42.8	20.4	38.0
M5	(Reference model)	48.4	42.6	43.5
M6	(Reference model)	63.0	60.1	59.3
M7	(Reference model)	46.2	38.6	39.4
M8	(Reference model)	35.2	26.4	30.1

tionary hypothesis. According to the Bayes factors it results that, among all the tested models, a template exponential distribution of IET with a linear function relating the logarithm of the distribution's μ parameter and the logarithm of the i_r is the best model describing the data (highest Bayes factor). Considering the categories defined in Table 1, the evidence in favor of this model against the stationary case is very strong. This result is obtained in all the model updates performed (i.e., M1 to M8).

This model, resulting from setting $n = 1$ in Eq. 4, is extremely interesting because it implies that the μ parameter and the i_r have a power-law relationship. It is worth noting that this model performs better than the linear relationship between seismicity rate and injection rate that is usually assumed in the literature. The implications of this finding are further analysed in the Discussion section. The parameter values of the *preferred* model selected at each M_i update are summarized in Table A1 and plotted in Fig. A1 in the Appendix D.

Fig. 5 shows the results (model fitting and the seismicity forecast using the preferred model) obtained adopting the *moving window* approach. Three examples, corresponding to the updated models M1 (Fig. 5a and 5b), M4 (Fig. 5c and 5d) and M8 (Fig. 5e and 5f), are shown. Left side plots in Fig. 5 show the data and the fitted competing models. The plots in the right side show the cumulated number of seismic events as a function of time (both observations and forecasts); the *learning part* of the catalog, used for model parameter estimation, is highlighted using a (green) shadowed area. Realizations of seismicity forecasts resulting from sampling the uncertainties in the model parameter values are shown using thin, gray lines; the seismicity forecasts are summarized by the median of the solutions (solid black line), whereas uncertainty bounds are defined showing the 16th and 84th percentiles (dashed black lines). The observed seismicity is shown with a solid, red line.

The analyses adopting the alternative *cumulated* approach indicate that, also in this case, the exponential distribution with the logarithm of the μ parameter linearly dependent on the logarithm of the injection rate is the preferred model (highest Bayes factor). The Bayes factors of competing models in three model updates (after 1, 3 and 5 years of data) are presented in Table 3. The parameter values obtained for the preferred models in these three updates are presented in Table A2 in the Appendix D.

Fig. 6 shows the results (model fitting and the seismicity

forecast using the preferred model) obtained adopting the cumulated approach. As in Fig. 5, the left side plots show the data and the competing models, and the right side plots show the comparison between the seismicity forecasts and the observations (colors and marks are the same as in Fig. 5).

Comparing the results obtained using both approaches, some interesting observations can be done. If we consider *near-time* forecasts (i.e., forecasting seismicity in a relatively short time window after t_c , e.g., a few months), both approaches produce acceptable results in which the median of the forecast solutions is very close to the observed seismicity (red lines in Figs. 5 and 6). However, if we consider *far-time* forecasts (i.e. forecasting seismicity using i_r data from times $t > 1$ year), we note that forecasts using the moving window approach reproduce a median value that is more coherent with the actual observations than the median of the forecasts produced using the cumulated approach (which in general tends to underestimate the seismicity rate).

If we consider the variability of the forecasts produced adopting these two strategies, the uncertainty range (defined between the 16th and the 84th percentiles of the solutions) tends to be smaller in the cumulated approach as the time window used for model parameter estimation increases. This behaviour is probably an effect of the lower uncertainty associated with the inference of model parameter values with a higher number of data points. We conclude that, in general, the moving window approach seems to produce better forecasts than the cumulated approach. In fact, a moving window approach, using the most recent part of the available data, is likely to be more sensitive to eventual changes in the seismic response of the system as a consequence of the perturbations (as e.g., permeability changes and/or pore-pressure perturbations near the injection well) caused by the fluid injections.

Note the long-lasting time windows of the forecasts presented in Figs. 5 and 6. Such long-lasting forecasts are feasible here because, for the sake of this exercise, we know the rate at which fluids were actually injected at these times; consequently, we use the full time series of the injection rate data available in the *forecasting part* of the catalog to analyze the model's behaviour. However, in an eventual application in which this model is used to forecast future seismicity according to *scheduled* injection rates, short-term forecasts are the outcome of primary interest.

Figure 6. Model parameter estimation and seismicity rate forecasts in The Geysers case study using the *cumulated window approach*. The first column shows the data and the competing deterministic models fitted. The second column shows the cumulated number of events as a function of time (observed and forecasts performed using the preferred, power-law model). Colors are the same as described in Fig. 5. The examples shown in this figure correspond to model fitting and seismicity forecasts using the first: (a, b) 2 years [M1* in Table A2]; (c, d) 3 years [M2*]; and (e, f) 5 years [M3*] of data.

4.2 Seismicity during the injection phases in the Cooper Basin case study

The data recorded during the injection phases in Cooper Basin have been used to infer possible relationships between fluid stimulations and seismicity rates. Since the seismic response after the start of the injection in Cooper Basin is al-

most immediate (the first seismic event was recorded about 20 minutes after the injection start), the lag time parameter τ in this case is neglected. It means that we consider that the system’s response to fluid injections is immediate.

First, we use the data related to the FIT-1 injection (IET and i_r) as the *learning part* of the catalog to determine the parameter values of the competing models. Table 4 (first

Table 3. Bayes factors B_{kl} calculated for model selection in The Geysers case study for models fitted using the cumulated window approach (M1* – M3*). For each M*, the highest Bayes factor is presented in bold.

Data used for model learning	$n = 0$	$2\text{Log}(B_{n0})$ [Degree of the polynomial function, Eq.4]		$2\text{Log}(B_{L0})$ [linear model as in Eq. 5]
		$n = 1$	$n = 2$	
M1*	(Reference model)	23.7	20.5	17.9
M2*	(Reference model)	75.8	64.1	70.7
M3*	(Reference model)	214.5	147.8	210.4

Figure 7. Data (IET of events plotted against the respective injection rate, gray dots) recorded during the FIT-1 injection test. The lines represent the plot of $\log(\mu(i_r))$ for fitted competing models (see the legend). The blue lines represents the *preferred* model: median (solid line), 16th and 84th percentiles (dashed lines).

Table 4. Bayes factors B_{kl} calculated for model selection in the Cooper Basin case study for models fitted using data from: the FIT-1 stimulation (top row), the FIT-3 stimulation (bottom row), and the aggregated data from FIT.1, FIT-2 and FIT-3 stimulations (middle row). For each case, the highest Bayes factor is presented in bold.

Data used for model learning	$n = 0$	$2\text{Log}(B_{n0})$ [Degree of the polynomial function, Eq.4]		$2\text{Log}(B_{L0})$ [linear model as in Eq. 5]
		$n = 1$	$n = 2$	
FIT-1	(Reference model)	34.6	33.8	30.6
FIT-1 to FIT-3	(Reference model)	96.8	93.9	92.3
FIT-3	(Reference model)	43.2	42.8	35.8

Figure 8. Cumulated number of events as a function of time (observed and forecast) during the FIT-3 test. The observed seismicity is plotted using a red, solid line. The seismicity rate forecast is performed using the preferred (power-law) model calibrated with the data from the FIT-1 injection. Realizations of seismicity forecasts are shown using thin, gray lines; the seismicity forecast is summarized by the median of the solutions (solid black line), whereas uncertainty bounds are defined showing the 16th and 84th percentiles (dashed black lines).

row) shows the Bayes factors calculated for comparing the performance of the NSM respect to the stationary hypothesis.

Analog to what was observed in The Geysers case study, the exponential distribution with the logarithm of the μ parameter linearly dependent on the logarithm of the injection rate is the preferred model (highest Bayes factor), implying therefore a power-law relationship between μ and i_r , also in this case. Considering the categories defined in Table 1, the evidence in favor of the power-law model (that is, the model resulting from setting $n = 1$ in Eq. 4) against the stationary case is very strong.

Fig. 7 shows the data (IET and related i_r during FIT-1, gray points) and the plot of the functions adjusted for the competing models. The parameter values obtained for the preferred model are presented in the first row of Table A3 in the Appendix D.

The data recorded during the FIT-3 and EXI injections (which were done respectively after 9 and 23 days of the FIT-1 test, see e.g., Fig. 2b) are selected as the *forecasting part* of the catalog; these two time intervals are used to test the forecasting performance of the model calibrated using the data recorded during the FIT-1. In practice, the injection rate data associated with both FIT-3 and EXI are used to evaluate the expected seismicity associated with these two injections according to the calibrated model. The seismicity forecast is then compared with the actual seismicity recorded during these injection phases.

The result of seismicity forecast (cumulated number of events as a function of time) obtained for the FIT-3 injection is shown in Fig. 8; the observed seismicity during the

FIT-3 injection is plotted using a red, solid line. Realizations of seismicity forecasts, resulting from sampling the uncertainties in the model parameter values, are shown using thin, gray lines; the seismicity forecast is summarized by the median of the solutions (solid black line), whereas uncertainty bounds are defined showing the 16th and 84th percentiles (dashed black lines).

The data set used for calibrating the model in this case (i.e., FIT-1) corresponds to an injection of about 101 m^3 of fluids in about 1.9 hours, during which 37 events above M_c were recorded. The FIT-3 test is characterized by a higher volume ($\sim 157 \text{ m}^3$) injected in about 12.9 hours (i.e., at a lower rate, see e.g. Fig. 4a), and with 75 seismic events above M_c associated. Taking into account the uncertainties in the model parameters, it can be considered that the variability of the forecast solutions enclose the observed seismicity within the 16th and 84th percentiles of the seismicity forecast.

Fig. 9 shows the cumulated number of events as a function of time for the main hydraulic stimulation (EXI). Colors and marks are the same as for Fig. 8. In Fig. 9a, the seismicity recorded during EXI is compared with the forecast produced by the model calibrated using the FIT-1 data only; it can be observed that the model forecast clearly underestimates the seismicity rates.

These two results indicate that the model calibrated with the FIT-1 data is able to describe to some extent the seismicity during the FIT-3 stimulation, but it results inadequate to describe the later main stimulation EXI (in this case, the observed seismicity is above the 84th percentile of the forecast solutions, see Fig.9a). It is plausible to suspect also in this

Figure 9. Cumulated number of events as a function of time (observed and forecasts) during the main hydraulic stimulation of Habanero-1 (EXI). Colors and marks are the same as in Fig. 8. The three forecasts presented in this figure were generated with the preferred (power-law) model calibrated using data from different stimulations preceding EXI: (a) model calibrated with FIT-1 data only; (b) model calibrated aggregating all the past injections (FIT-1 to FIT-3); and (c) model calibrated with FIT-3 data only.

case that changes in the medium properties (as e.g., a perturbed pore pressure distribution caused by precedent injections, and/or changes in permeability as fractures grow) may induce changes in the seismic response of the system to the hydraulic stimulations.

To assess this hypothesis, two strategies for selecting the *learning part* of the catalog used to update the model (as well as the seismicity forecast related to the EXI stimulation) were tested: A first strategy to update the model was performed by using the aggregated data of all the injection periods from FIT-1 to FIT-3 (i.e., using all the data from the injection phases preceding the EXI, analog to the cumulated window approach used in The Geysers case). In agreement with the result obtained using the FIT-1 data only, a template exponential distribution with a linear function relating the logarithm of both μ and i_r is selected as the preferred model (the Bayes factors are presented in Table 4, second row). The model parameter values obtained for the preferred model using this data are presented in the second row of Table A3 in the Appendix D. The derived seismicity rate forecasts for the EXI stimulation are presented in Fig. 9b. Compared to the seismicity forecast performed using the model derived from the FIT-1 injection, the model obtained using all the injection phases preceding EXI performs a little bit better (the observed seismicity is close to the 84th percentile of the solutions); nevertheless, most of the sampled solutions still tend to underestimate the seismicity.

A second strategy to update the model was to use as the *learning part* the FIT-3 data only (i.e. using only the data from the last stimulation preceding the EXI). Also in this case, a linear function linking the logarithms of both μ and i_r results as the preferred model (Bayes factors in Table 4, third row), with model parameter values as those presented in Table A3 (third row, Appendix D). As in the previous cases, the evidence supporting this model respect to the reference model is very strong (according to the categories defined in Table 1). The seismicity rate forecast produced by the model adjusted using the FIT-3 data is presented in Fig. 9c; in this case the seismicity rate forecast results more coherent with the observed seismicity, which in this case is closer to the median of the forecasting solutions respect to the previous two cases presented in Fig. 9a and 9b.

Comparing the forecasts shown in Fig. 9 it can be concluded that in the Cooper Basin case study, forecasting seismicity rates calibrating the model with the most recent injection data (e.g., FIT-3 for analyzing the EXI stimulation) produces better results than using all the data recorded during the past injection tests. This behaviour is similar to the result obtained adopting the *moving window* approach in The Geysers case.

It is worth to note how this simple model, calibrated using the data from a relatively small injection test, is able to produce acceptable forecasts of the seismicity expected during a later stimulation which is about 17 times longer in time and characterized by the injection of a 90 times larger volume of fluids. In fact, considering the example shown in Fig. 9c, the model has been calibrated using a stimulation episode (the FIT-3) characterized by the injection of about 157 m^3 of fluids in about 12.9 hours (with associated 75 seismic events above M_c), and it is used to model the seismicity associated with the main hydraulic stimulation (EXI) which is charac-

terized by the injection of about 14600 m³ of fluids in about 9.4 days (with associated 11334 events above M_c).

4.3 Seismicity during the free-response phases in the Cooper Basin case

The seismicity rates during the FRPs in Cooper Basin were studied in the time intervals in which enough data was available to model the seismicity rate decay using the MOL model (Eq. 7). Fitting a model to the seismicity recorded during a FRP is not always a feasible task, especially when the time between two injections is too short so that the seismicity rate decay cannot be properly observed. Four FRPs, corresponding to the phases following the FIT-1, FIT-2, LTI, and FIT-3 injections, were identified (Fig. 10). Hereinafter, these FRPs are called using the same code used for the preceding injection episode (i.e. FIT1-FRP, FIT2-FRP, LTI-FRP, and FIT3-FRP).

The analysis of the LTI-FRP, however, is particularly challenging mainly because the FIT-3 injection took place when the seismic sequence during LTI-FRP was still very active. Furthermore, it is possible that the seismic sequence in this period includes also aftershock events developed after a M3.0 event (the one with the highest magnitude in this FRP, see Fig. 10). As a consequence, the time window of the LTI-FRP does not properly capture the decay of the seismicity rate, and for this reason this FRP is not considered in this analysis.

Table 5 summarizes the MOL parameter values obtained for the three FRPs analysed (which are basically the post-injection phases following the fracture initiation tests); in Table 5, *MaxL* refers to values obtained using the maximum Likelihood estimator, whereas *mcmc* refers to the median values obtained using the MCMC approach. The uncertainties in the values inferred for these parameters are not reported in Table 5 but are graphically presented in Fig. 11. Table 5 shows also the average injection rate and the total injected volume of the injection preceding the corresponding FRP.

In agreement with different published works (e.g., Langenbruch & Shapiro 2010; Bachmann et al. 2011; Langenbruch & Zoback 2016), the values of the p parameter characterizing the seismicity decay rate during the FRPs in Cooper Basin (according to the MOL) are in general higher than the values usually found for natural seismicity. To check if the obtained values of p are somehow correlated with the main characteristics of the preceding fluid injections, we plot the values of p against both the total injected volume (Fig. 11a) and the average injection rate (Fig. 11b) of the stimulation immediately preceding each FRP analysed. The lowest value of the p exponent seems to be associated with the stimulation with the higher average injection rate and injected volume; nevertheless, the available data is very limited to draw any reliable conclusion in this regard.

Fig. 12 shows the cumulated number of events (observed and modelled with the MOL) as a function of time for each FRP analysed. In these plots, the observed seismicity is plotted using solid circles. The median of the simulated seismicity using the MOL model is plotted using a solid line, whereas the dashed lines represent the 16th and 84th percentiles of the simulations. It can be seen that the MOL pro-

vides an adequate description of the seismicity during these FRPs.

An interesting feature of the MCMC solution implemented in this work is that possible co-dependences between the c and the p parameters can be identified and considered for the seismicity forecasts performed using the MOL. Such a kind of correlations among the parameters of scaling laws describing the behaviour of aftershock sequences has been investigated both theoretically and empirically in many papers [see e.g., the discussion presented in Gasperini & Lolli (2006) considering different models, and in Holschneider et al. (2012) for the MOL in particular]. For example, Fig. 11c shows a representation of the posterior density of $\{c, p\}$ for the FIT3-FRP, where it is possible to see the co-dependence between these two parameters. The modelled seismicity (median and uncertainty bounds) presented in Fig. 12 are generated taking into account the co-dependence of the MOL parameters.

5 DISCUSSION

In this paper we study relationships between fluid-induced seismicity and operational parameters from related fluid-injections. In particular, we introduce a stochastic model, based on a covariate approach, to model seismicity during sustained fluid injections. The proposed methodology has the following key features:

- (i) Virtually any probability distribution valid for describing IETs can be implemented. For example, in the data analyses performed in this research, the Weibull distribution was also considered as a possible template probabilistic model. Nevertheless, the exponential model always performed better than the Weibull (according to Bayes factors).
- (ii) Different deterministic functions linking the parameter(s) of the probability distribution and operational parameters can be explored and the most adequate solution selected.
- (iii) Once the model has been selected and calibrated for the induced seismicity in a given area, it can be used to forecast seismicity rates according to scheduled fluid injections.

The performance of the presented modelling approach was tested using data from two examples of seismicity induced by operations in geothermal systems (The Geysers, US, and Cooper Basin, Australia). We have found that a template exponential distribution of IET, with a linear function relating the logarithm of the distribution's μ parameter and the logarithm of the injection rate, is the model that better describes the observations in all the injection phases analysed in this work. That is:

$$\log[\mu(i_r)] = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \log[i_r]$$

This finding suggests that the μ parameter of the exponential distribution of IET and the injection rate have a power-law relationship of the form:

$$\mu(i_r) = \alpha'_0 [i_r]^{\alpha_1} \quad (8)$$

where α'_0 is a proportionality constant, with $\alpha_0 = \log(\alpha'_0)$. The power-law relationship indicates that a relative change in the injection rate gives rise to a proportional relative change in the seismicity rate λ [with $\lambda(i_r) = 1/\mu(i_r)$]. This result, in general, confirms the established assumption

Figure 10. Free-response phases identified in the Cooper Basin data set before the main stimulation (EXI).

that the seismicity rate increases with increasing the fluid injection rate; however, the exponent α_1 becomes an important parameter to describe the behaviour of the seismicity as the injection rate increases.

When $\alpha_1 = -1$, the relationship between seismicity rate and injection rate is linear, as is usually assumed in the literature (Fig. 13, solid, red line). $\alpha_1 > -1$ ($\alpha_1 < -1$) indicates that the relative change in the seismicity rate associated with a relative change in the injection rate is lower (higher) than the relative change expected by assuming a linear model between these two parameters (see dashed lines in Fig. 13).

From a physical point of view, high injection rates are usually correlated with elevated pore pressure in the vicinity of injection wells; for this reason, the correlation between seismicity rates and injection rates is generally motivated with pore pressure variations. The shear and the effective normal stresses acting on a fault depend on the magnitudes of the principal stresses, the pore pressure, and the orientation of the fault with respect to the principal stresses. When the pore pressure increases, the effective normal stress resolved on preexisting fractures is reduced and slip is stimulated mainly in favorably-oriented faults; however, at extremely high pore pressure it is possible to induce slip also in non well-oriented faults (see e.g., Zoback 2010).

High pore-pressure perturbations have been suggested as the dominant triggering mechanism of the seismicity in

both cases analysed in this paper. Regarding the seismicity in the Cooper Basin case, Asanuma et al. (2005a) and Baisch et al. (2006) suggested that induced events in Cooper Basin primarily consist of shear events on patches of a pre-existing fracture zone, and that the reduction of the effective normal stress (driven by the increased pore pressure) is the dominating triggering mechanism of seismicity. On the other hand, regarding The Geysers data set, Martínez-Garzón et al. (2016) have found that effectively a great proportion of the seismicity in this data set occurs on faults with favorable orientation for failure with respect to the stress field; however, an important number of events are observed either to occur on severely mis-oriented faults or to slip in a different orientation than predicted from the stress field, and these events mostly occur during periods of high injection rates.

An accurate determination of the α_1 parameter is therefore an important element to better characterize the relationship between seismicity rates and injection rates, as well as to produce more accurate seismicity rate forecast associated with fluid injections. The α_1 values obtained in this study for the two data sets analysed vary in the range -1.22 to -0.73 in the Cooper Basin case, and from -1.04 to -0.78 in The Geysers case.

Considering however the temporal evolution of the calculated parameters it can be observed that, in Cooper basin, α_1 changes from an initial value of $\alpha_1 = -1.22$ during the FIT-1, to $\alpha_1 = -0.73$ during the FIT-3 (see Table A3),

Figure 11. Plot of the MOL p parameter as a function of (a) the injected volume and (b) the injection rate of the stimulation preceding the respective free-response phase in the Cooper Basin test case. (c) Representation of the posterior density of $\{c, p\}$ for the FIT3-FRP (dark colors indicate higher density).

Figure 12. Cumulative number of events (observed and modelled using the MOL) as a function of time for the three free-response phases analysed: (a) FIT1-FRP; (b) FIT2-FRP; (c) FIT3-FRP. (d) cumulated number of events observed during the LTI-FRP.

Table 5. MOL model parameter values for the three free-response phases analysed in the Cooper Basin case study. The first number corresponds to the value obtained using the MCMC approach, whereas the number within the square brackets is the initial value obtained using the maximum likelihood (MaxL) approach.

FRP	p^{mcmc} [p^{MaxL}]	c^{mcmc} [c^{MaxL}]	k^{mcmc} [k^{MaxL}]	average injection rate (l/s)	Injected volume (m ³)
FIT1-FRP	2.20 [2.70]	0.01 [0.30]	0.60 [10]	14.8	101.1
FIT2-FRP	1.60 [1.02]	0.01 [0.01]	1.20 [10]	16.7	198.4
FIT3-FRP	2.70 [2.70]	1.01 [1.40]	137 [130]	3.4	157.2

which is the last injection test preceding the main extended stimulation EX1. Such an increasing trend in the α_1 exponent implies that the relative increase in seismicity rate associated with a given increase in the injection rate is more pronounced during the first injections. This change could be directly related to the injection history and possibly associated with a process usually known in material sciences as the *Kaiser effect* (Kaiser 1950). According to this phenomenon, a fracture *remembers* the maximum fluid pressure it has previously experienced; therefore, to trigger new events it is necessary that the pore pressure exceeds maximum values already reached in previous stimulations. Evidences of the Kaiser effect in the Cooper Basin seismicity were already suggested by Baisch et al. (2006) after observing the extremely small distance between hypocenter locations and the seismic quiescence behind a propagating triggering front.

The values of the α_1 exponent obtained for The Geysers are in general $\alpha_1 \gtrsim -1$. Looking at the temporal variation of the α_0 and α_1 parameters resulting from the updating process (see e.g. Fig. A1 in the Appendix D), they seem to exhibit correlated long-term oscillations. Correlated changes in α_0 and α_1 result also evident in the model updates in Cooper Basin, as can be seen in Table A3 (Appendix D). It is difficult to establish if such oscillations have a link to any physical process associated with the mechanical response of the reservoir or if they are just a trade-off effect resulting from the inference of the model parameter values. In general, however, the median α_1 values in The Geysers are greater than -1 , indicating that the seismicity rate increases with i_r at a lower rate respect to what would be predicted assuming a linear model.

The performance of the calibrated models is assessed by comparing seismicity rate forecasts produced by the model with the observed seismicity rates. The model is trained using a subset of data of the catalog and the forecasting capability is assessed for the remaining period. The forecast exercise is performed taking as input the operational data (injection rate in these examples) for forecasting the expected induced seismicity rates.

It has been found that models calibrated using the most recent past data produce forecasts that are more coherent with the observations. This behaviour may suggest that, as the fluid stimulations proceed, changes in the physical properties of the stimulated reservoir (as e.g., the pore pressure near the well, or the permeability) may induce changes in the seismic response of the system.

It is worth noting that, in this paper, the comparison between observed seismicity rates and the model's forecasts is performed using all the injection data available in the forecasting time windows selected for testing the model.

It implies performing forecasts in time windows lasting hours/days in the Cooper basin case (see e.g., Figs. 8 and 9), or even years in The Geysers case (see e.g., Figs. 5 and 6). In real forecasting applications, however, both the order of magnitude of the fluid-induced perturbations and the future operations may be uncertain; consequently, in such a case it makes more sense to use the model to produce short-term seismicity rate forecasts considering realistic, near-future, injection scenarios (i.e., from days to few months).

The main scope of the work presented in this paper is to study the stochastic behaviour of fluid-induced seismicity during injection phases. However, the Cooper Basin data set exhibits fluid injection episodes alternated with non-injection phases (i.e., FRP), and the seismicity in such phases in general exhibits the usual gradual decline of seismicity rates as time passes. With a limited number of FRPs from the Cooper Basin data set we explored the possibility to identify any pattern between the parameters controlling the post-injection seismicity decay rate, modelled using the MOL model, and the characteristics of the precedent fluid injection.

In agreement with previous works focused in the analysis of post-injection seismicity (as e.g., Langenbruch & Shapiro 2010; Langenbruch & Zoback 2016), the values of the MOL's p parameter in FRPs in Cooper Basin are in general higher than the values usually found for natural seismicity. Considering in particular the characteristics of the preceding injection operation, the lower value of p in this case seems to be associated with the stimulation characterized by the higher average injection rate and higher injected volume. Nevertheless, the available data points in the studied example are too few to draw any reliable conclusion in this regard. It therefore remains as an open question to be further explored using a more extended data set.

The methodology presented in this paper for modelling induced seismicity during fluid injection phases is developed for the analysis of seismic sequences in the time domain. We started from assuming that fluid injections are the dominant mechanism generating seismicity, neglecting the possibility of earthquake interactions. The forthcoming steps in this research are oriented towards extending the analyses to consider possible earthquake interactions, the spatial domain and the magnitude distribution of the seismic events.

6 CONCLUSIONS

We present a novel covariate approach to model seismic sequences occurring during sustained fluid injections. In the proposed model, a probability distribution is defined as a ba-

Figure 13. Plot of the expected seismicity rates (in events/day) as a function of the injection rate (in l/s) for different values of the exponent α_1 (and setting $\alpha_0' = 1$). The continuous red line corresponds to the particular case $\alpha_1 = -1.0$, which implies a linear relationship between the seismicity rate and the injection rate.

seismic template function for modelling the IET between consecutive seismic events, whereas possible dependencies on operational parameters are modelled writing the parameters of the probabilistic model in terms of deterministic functions of explanatory covariates selected from the operational data. The main findings resulting from this study can be summarized as follows:

(i) The exponential distribution with a linear function relating the logarithm of the distribution's μ parameter and the logarithm of the injection rate, is the model providing the best description of the IET observed in the fluid-induced seismic sequences analysed in this paper.

(ii) The previous result suggests that seismicity rate and injection rate have a power-law relationship.

(iii) The value of the power-law exponent, α_1 , is an indicator of the relative change in the seismicity rate associated to a relative change in the injection rate, and it results particularly important for understanding the behaviour of seismicity at high injection rates.

(iv) $\alpha_1 = -1$ indicates the special case of a linear relationship between seismicity rate and injection rate; conversely, $\alpha_1 > -1$ ($\alpha_1 < -1$) indicates that the relative change in the seismicity rate associated to a relative change in the injection rate is lower (higher) than the relative change expected by assuming a linear model between these two pa-

rameters (which is the usual assumption adopted *a priori* in the literature).

(v) In the Cooper basin case study, the α_1 exponent changed from an initial value of $\alpha_1 = -1.22$ (associated with the first fracture initiation test) to $\alpha_1 = -0.73$ (associated with the third fracture initiation test). It means that the relative increase in seismicity rate caused by a determined increase in the injection rate is greater in early injections. This behaviour can be a consequence of the so-called Kaiser effect, indicating that to trigger events, the pore pressure during new injections must exceed values already reached in previous injection operations.

(vi) The model produces best seismicity rate forecasts when it is calibrated using a moving time-window approach (i.e. using a time window covering the most recent data only). This behaviour is probably a consequence of the changes in the system induced by the fluid injections (as e.g., changes in permeability, or changes associated with phenomena as the Kaiser effect).

Finally, regarding the inference of model parameter values, we implement Bayesian methods for model parameter estimation. The added value of this strategy is that such methods are extremely flexible (a) for model implementation and testing, (b) for assessing possible co-dependences among model parameters, and (c) as a natural framework for handling uncertainties.

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APPENDIX A: FAMILY OF POLYNOMIAL FUNCTIONS USED AS TEST MODELS LINKING μ AND THE INJECTION RATE

In the approach proposed in this paper we write the parameters of IET distributions using deterministic functions of the injection rate. We tested and compared the performance of both the exponential and the Weibull distributions with covariates and found that, according to the Bayes factors, the exponential model with covariates was always the preferred model when analyzing the two data sets considered in this paper.

The μ parameter of the exponential distribution is written using deterministic functions of the injection rate. We test polynomial functions relating $\log(\mu)$ and $\log(i_r)$ as shown in Eq. 4:

$$\log[\mu(i_r)] = \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_j (\log[i_r])^j \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\alpha_j = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$ is a vector of coefficients of the polynomial function relating the model parameter of the distribution with the identified covariate. It results in a family of possible models, as for example a stationary model ($n = 0$), a linear trend ($n = 1$), an so on for higher order polynomial functions:

$$\log[\mu(i_r)] = \begin{cases} \alpha_0 & \text{for } n = 0 \\ \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \log[i_r] & \text{for } n = 1 \\ \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \log[i_r] + \alpha_2 (\log[i_r])^2 & \text{for } n = 2 \\ \dots & \dots \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

In the case of the Weibull distribution with covariates,

$$f(t^* | a, b) = b a^{-b} (t^*)^{b-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t^*}{a}\right)^b} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

the a and b parameters of the Weibull distribution is written as a function of the injection rate according to:

$$\begin{aligned} \log[a(i_r)] &= \sum_{j=0}^m \beta_j (\log[i_r])^j \\ \log[b(i_r)] &= \sum_{j=0}^k \gamma_j (\log[i_r])^j \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

APPENDIX B: THE LAPLACE-METROPOLIS ESTIMATOR USED TO CALCULATE MARGINAL LIKELIHOODS

The Bayes factor, B_{kl} , for comparing model M_k to Model M_l for observed data \mathbf{x} , is the ratio of the posterior odds for M_k against M_l to the prior odds. When the models M_k and M_l are equally probable a priori, then B_{kl} reduces to:

$$B_{kl} = \frac{f(\mathbf{x} | M_k)}{f(\mathbf{x} | M_l)}$$

It implies computing the marginal likelihoods for model M_m (also called the integrated likelihood, marginal probability of the data, or predictive probability of the data) which has the form (e.g., Kass & Raftery 1995; Lewis & Raftery 1997):

$$f(\mathbf{x} | M_m) = \int f(\mathbf{x} | \theta_m, M_m) f(\theta_m | M_m) d\theta_m \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where θ_m is the vector of parameters in model M_m , and $f(\theta_m | M_m)$ is its prior density.

The marginal likelihoods, required to compute the Bayes factor, are calculated using the Laplace-Metropolis (LM) estimator (Raftery 1996; Lewis & Raftery 1997). Letting $h = \log\{f(\theta)f(\mathbf{x}|\theta)\}$ (the conditioning respect to M_m , as shown in Eq. B.1, was dropped for simplicity) and applying the Laplace approximation for an integral, the following approximation for the marginal likelihood is obtained (Raftery 1996; Lewis & Raftery 1997):

$$f(\mathbf{x}) \approx (2\pi)^{P/2} |\mathbf{H}^*|^{1/2} f(\theta^*) f(\mathbf{x}|\theta^*) \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where θ^* is the value of θ at which h attains its maximum and \mathbf{H}^* is minus the inverse Hessian of h evaluated at θ^* (Lewis & Raftery 1997). For numerical reasons we use Eq. B.2 in a logarithmic scale ($\log\{f(\mathbf{x})\}$).

The marginal likelihood is calculated using the samples of the posterior distribution generated by the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. In practice, the components of θ^* are estimated calculating the component-wise posterior medians from the sample, whereas \mathbf{H}^* , being asymptotically equal to the posterior variance matrix, is estimated using the sample covariance matrix of the posterior simulation output.

APPENDIX C: INFERENCE OF THE MOL PARAMETER VALUES

According to the MOL (Omori 1894; Utsu 1961), the decay rate of seismicity after a given triggering event can be described as:

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{k}{(c+t)^p}$$

where $\lambda(t)$ is the number of events in the unit time; k is usually known as the productivity of aftershocks; t is the elapsed time since the triggering event (in this case the preceding fluid injection); p is the power-law exponent; and c is a parameter partially reflecting the effect of incomplete detection of small events shortly after the triggering event (Utsu et al. 1995). According to some authors c can be also considered as the time delay at which the decay rate initiates (e.g. Holschneider et al. 2012).

The MOL parameter values are determined using two different approaches: a classical Maximum Likelihood approach (e.g., Ogata 1983), and a Bayesian approach based on a MCMC method that uses the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm (Metropolis & Ulam 1949; Metropolis et al. 1953).

We use the parameterization proposed by Holschneider et al. (2012), in which the MOL is rewritten as, for $p \neq 1$:

$$\lambda(t) = \Lambda \frac{D(c,p)}{(1 + \frac{t}{c})^p} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

with $t > 0$ and where

$$D(c,p) = \frac{(1-p)}{c} \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{t_e}{c})^{1-p} - (1 + \frac{t_0}{c})^{1-p}}$$

while for $p = 1$,

$$\lambda(t) = \Lambda \frac{D(c,p=1)}{(1 + \frac{t}{c})} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

with $t > 0$ and where

$$D(c,p=1) = \frac{1/c}{\log(1 + \frac{t_e}{c}) - \log(1 + \frac{t_0}{c})}$$

In this parameterization, p and c maintain their meaning, while Λ is the Poissonian rate of the total number of events in the observation interval $[t_i, t_e]$, i.e., the expected number of events during this time interval (Holschneider et al. 2012):

$$\Lambda = E(\text{number of events in } [t_i, t_e]) = \frac{k/c^p}{D(c,p)}$$

The advantage of using this parametrization is that in this way the productivity is decoupled from the other two parameters (c and p), becoming also an observational constraint directly defined from the data (Holschneider et al. 2012).

In the analysis implemented in this work, the solutions obtained using the MaxL approach are used to initialize the MCMC sampler (used for the Bayesian estimation) in the parameter space. This procedure improves the performance of the MCMC sampler (faster convergence).

The prior distribution for the c and p parameters is set using an uniform distribution in the log space, which is defined using wide bounds. The results obtained using the MCMC approach allow us to assess the stability of the obtained solutions and to take into account possible co-dependences of the c and p model parameters for the seismicity forecasts obtained using the MOL model (details regarding this issue can be found in Holschneider et al. 2012).

APPENDIX D: VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS OF PREFERRED (POWER-LAW) MODELS SELECTED IN THE STUDIED CASES

In this appendix we summarize the obtained parameter values of the preferred models in the analysed cases: The Geysers case (Table A1 for the moving window approach, and Table A2 for the cumulated window approach), and the Cooper Basin (Table A3).

Considering in particular the model parameter values in The Geysers case study, Fig. A1 shows the α_j parameter values of the preferred models fitted using the moving window approach (M1 to M8), where it is possible to see correlated variations of the α_0 and the α_1 as they are updated.

Table A1. Model parameter values of the deterministic models selected as preferred models for describing the relationship between the μ parameter of the exponential template distribution and the injection rate (The Geysers case study using the moving window approach). Models in **bold** are those represented in Fig. 5.

Data for model parameter estimation			Parameter values			
Model n.	Start time	End time	α_0 (α'_0) [median]	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 16^{th} \text{ perc} \\ 84^{th} \text{ perc} \end{array} \right.$	α_1 [median]	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 16^{th} \text{ perc} \\ 84^{th} \text{ perc} \end{array} \right.$
M1	10-Dec-2007	19-May-2009	2.427 (267.3)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1.983 \\ 2.973 \end{array} \right.$	-0.889	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.143 \\ -0.702 \end{array} \right.$
M2	20-May-2008	18-Nov-2009	2.141 (138.4)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1.851 \\ 2.438 \end{array} \right.$	-0.783	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.935 \\ -0.646 \end{array} \right.$
M3	18-Nov-2008	19-May-2010	2.211 (162.6)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1.927 \\ 2.438 \end{array} \right.$	-0.871	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.974 \\ -0.740 \end{array} \right.$
M4	20-May-2009	18-Nov-2010	2.566 (368.1)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2.272 \\ 3.316 \end{array} \right.$	-1.040	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.379 \\ -0.890 \end{array} \right.$
M5	18-Nov-2009	19-May-2011	2.338 (217.8)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2.041 \\ 2.774 \end{array} \right.$	-0.944	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.128 \\ -0.813 \end{array} \right.$
M6	20-May-2010	18-Nov-2011	2.394 (247.7)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2.150 \\ 2.589 \end{array} \right.$	-0.956	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.051 \\ -0.858 \end{array} \right.$
M7	18-Nov-2010	18-May-2012	2.005 (101.2)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1.383 \\ 2.327 \end{array} \right.$	-0.816	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.953 \\ -0.547 \end{array} \right.$
M8	20-May-2011	17-Nov-2012	2.375 (237.1)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1.687 \\ 2.941 \end{array} \right.$	-0.980	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.238 \\ -0.673 \end{array} \right.$

Table A2. Model parameter values of the deterministic models selected as preferred models for describing the relationship between the μ parameter of the exponential template distribution and the injection rate (The Geysers case study using the cumulated window approach).

Data for model parameter estimation			Parameter values			
Model n.	Start time	End time	α_0 (α'_0) [median]	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 16^{th} \text{ perc} \\ 84^{th} \text{ perc} \end{array} \right.$	α_1 [median]	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 16^{th} \text{ perc} \\ 84^{th} \text{ perc} \end{array} \right.$
M1*	10-Dec-2007	09-Dec-2009	2.117 (130.9)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1.848 \\ 2.321 \end{array} \right.$	-0.757	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.839 \\ -0.622 \end{array} \right.$
M2*	10-Dec-2007	09-Dec-2010	2.451 (282.5)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2.123 \\ 3.023 \end{array} \right.$	-0.949	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.215 \\ -0.810 \end{array} \right.$
M3*	10-Dec-2007	09-Dec-2012	2.478 (300.6)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2.330 \\ 2.640 \end{array} \right.$	-0.989	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.064 \\ -0.925 \end{array} \right.$

Table A3. Model parameter values of the deterministic models selected as preferred models for describing the relationship between the μ parameter of the exponential template distribution and the injection rate in the analysed injection periods in the Cooper basin case study.

Data used for parameter estimation	α_0 (α'_0) [median]	Parameter values		
		$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 16^{th} \text{ perc} \\ 84^{th} \text{ perc} \end{array} \right.$	α_1 [median]	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 16^{th} \text{ perc} \\ 84^{th} \text{ perc} \end{array} \right.$
FIT-1	-0.736 (0.184)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.228 \\ -0.249 \end{array} \right.$	-1.222	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.483 \\ -0.931 \end{array} \right.$
FIT-1 to FIT-3	-1.339 (0.046)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.531 \\ -1.167 \end{array} \right.$	-0.852	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.972 \\ -0.723 \end{array} \right.$
FIT-3	-1.478 (0.033)	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -1.678 \\ -1.304 \end{array} \right.$	-0.732	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -0.879 \\ -0.596 \end{array} \right.$

Figure A1. Plot of the α_j parameter values of the preferred (power-law) models fitted using the moving window approach (M1 to M8) for The Geysers case study.